

ISSN 0976-559X

VĀGĪŚVARĪ

Multilingual Research Journal
Volume – XI

DEPARTMENT OF SANSKRIT
ASSAM UNIVERSITY
SILCHAR
2016

*Susmita Purkayastha
01/10/22*

Contents

		Page
• वागीश्वरी - प्रशस्ति		1
• संस्कृतवन्दनम्		2
1 तैत्तिरीयोपनिषदि आनन्दतत्त्वम्	अध्यापिका स्वप्ना देवी	3
2 विदुरनीतिः : विहङ्गमदृष्टिरेका	डॉ शान्ति पोखरेल	6
3 उपमानप्रमाणपरीक्षणम्	डॉ गोविन्द शर्मा	13
4 नात्वकाररूपेण श्रीकृष्णमिश्रः : एकं समीक्षणम्	ज्ञानश्री देवी	17
5 Skandasvāmin – The Commentator of the Ṛgveda	Snigdha Das Roy	20
6 Lord Jagannath and Nimbarka Philosophy : A Brief Analysis	Bhagirathi Biswas	24
7 The Gaudiya Vaishnava Canon : A Critical Study of the <i>Brahmasamhita</i>	Jaydeep Chakrabarty	29
8 Medical science in Vedic India with reference to the Brāhmaṇa literature	Milan Barman	35
9 Treatment of Fractures and Dislocations in the Suśruta Saṁhitā	Hiten Barman	38
10 Sanskrit : A Scientific Language	Dimple Barman	45
11 Dramaturgy in Nāṭyaśāstra, Daśarūpaka and Sāhityadarpaṇa : A brief Analysis	Mukul Chandra Ray	52
12 Laws of Witness in Ancient and Modern Indian	Susmita Purkayastha	59
13 Business Practices and Commercialisation in Dharmasūtric Perspective: A Glimpse	Sanu Sinha	65
14 संस्कृतभाषा-सहित्य चर्चाय कोच राजदरवार : एकटि अध्यायन	कमल राय	73

LAWS OF WITNESS IN ANCIENT AND MODERN INDIAN

Susmita Purkayastha

Introduction :

This paper deals with the rules of evidence of witnesses in ancient and modern India. Proof of any dispute (civil or criminal) is through the evidence placed before the judge or the magistrate and recorded by him. The Judge forms his judgment from such evidence. Rarely, as in cases of contempt of court or an offence committed in his presence, does the judge act on his personal and direct knowledge. The evidence adduced before him is either documentary, or oral, or possessory, or supernatural (or divine). But out of all these types of evidence, the importance of oral evidence cannot be exaggerated. A documents is always proved by some witness, who is either an attesting witness, or the scribe, or the executants, or one, who proves the genuineness of the document. Possession is proved by witnesses who state the fact of possession or prove documents, like deeds of gift, mortgage, lease etc. even in cases of special oaths or ordeals, the contentions of the disputed parties have to be sworn before the court, before the necessity of special oaths or ordeals arises. Therefore, oral evidence is of great importance for a study of the law of evidence. Besides this, the vast majority of cases, specially criminal cases depend on oral evidence. Therefore, though lawgivers like Yājñavalkya and later commentators give pride of place to documentary evidence on account of the greater weight attached to it (and rightly so), yet oral evidence is of very great importance for a study of law of evidence in Ancient India. Oral evidence is either direct or indirect or hearsay. Direct evidence may be called primary evidence and hearsay evidence may be called secondary evidence; though the Indian Evidence Act uses the terms 'primary' and 'secondary' in respect of documentary evidence.

Direct Evidence

The most fundamental principle of the law of evidence is that direct evidence is admissible and preferred. Wherever direct evidence is either available or likely to be available, hearsay evidence is inadmissible. Hearsay evidence is admitted only under exceptional circumstance and sometimes as corroborative of direct evidence.

* PhD Research Scholar, Department of Sanskrit, Assam University.

The Vedas on direct evidence

The Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa says "truth is the eye, therefore if two persons disputing come and one of them says 'I have seen' and the other says 'I have heard' the person who says 'I have seen' should be believed".³⁵

If the evidence refers to a fact which could be heard, the statement of a witness, who says that he heard it, it is direct evidence. But when a fact could be seen, the statement of a person who saw it himself is direct evidence. The statement of person who says that he heard it from a person, who saw it, is hearsay and not be admissible.

Viṣṇu and Manu on direct evidence

Ancient lawgivers in India must have seen the many problems that arise when hearsay evidence is tendered or admitted.

Viṣṇu says: A person is a witness because he has seen an occurrence or has heard about it.³⁶ Manu also says "only a person who has seen an event happening can depose to having seen it and on matters which are capable of being heard, one who has heard it can depose and prove it".³⁷

Medhātithi, The commentator of Manusmṛiti, commenting on the above proposition says that hearsay evidence occurs, when a person hears from another, who has himself heard from another and comes forward as a witness and that hearsay is no evidence.

Nārada on direct evidence

Nārada also states that when two persons are litigating and there is a doubt, or discrepancy between the two, the determination of the dispute is due to witnesses, people who have seen or heard are proper witnesses.³⁸ A matter which can be seen is deposed to by an eye witness. A matter which can be heard (e.g. defamatory statements, abuses etc.) can be proved by one who heard such words.

The Indian Evidence Act (Section 60)

The great value attached to direct evidence is borne out by section 60, which may be taken as a definition of direct evidence. It says – "Oral evidence must in all cases be direct, that is to say –

'If it refers to a fact which could be seen, it must be the evidence of a witness who says he saw it; 'If it refers to a fact which could be heard, it must be the evidence of a witness who says he heard it; 'If it refers to a fact which could be perceived by any other sense, or in any other manner, it must be the evidence of a witness who says, he perceived to it by

³⁵ सत्यं वै चक्षुः सत्यं हि वे चक्षुस्तस्माद्यदिदानीं दृवी विवदमानावेयातामहमदवाश्रमहमदवाश्रमहमश्रीचमिति य एवं ब्रूयादहमद्राक्षमिति तस्मा एव श्रदध्यात्॥ SB 14-8-15-5.

³⁶ समक्षदर्शनात्साक्षी श्रवणाद्वा॥ Viṣṇu- VIII.3.

³⁷ समक्षदर्शनात्साक्षी श्रवणाद्यैव सिध्यति। Manu- VIII.174.

³⁸ समक्षदर्शनात्साक्षी विशेषः क्षेत्रचक्षुषोः।

श्रीचस्य यत्परो ब्रूते चक्षुषोदेशनं ध्रुवम्। Nārada- IV.148.

that sense or in that manner. 'If it refers to an opinion or to the grounds on which that opinion is held, it must be the evidence of the person who holds that opinion on those grounds.

'Provided that the opinions of experts expressed in any treatise commonly offered for sale and on grounds, on which such opinions are held may be proved by the production of such treatises, if the author is dead or cannot be found or has become incapable of giving evidence or cannot be called as a witness without an amount of delay, or expense, which the court regards as unreasonable.

'Provided also, that if oral evidence refers to the existence or condition of any material thing other than a document, the court may, if it thinks fit, require the production of such material thing for its inspection."

Hearsay

Various modern definitions of 'hearsay' are given. Taylor defines it as "ass the evidence, which does not derive its value solely from the credit giver to the witness himself, but which rests also in part on the veracity and competence of some other persons".³⁹

Bentham defines it as "the supposed oral testimony transmitted through oral : supposed orally delivered evidence of a supposed extra judicially narrating witness judicially delivered viva voce by the judicially deposing witness".

Phipson says, 'oral or written statements of persons not called as witnesses are inadmissible to prove the truth of the matters stated except in the cases hereinafter mentioned". (The exceptions are discussed below).

Phipson also says "the term 'hearsay' though in its usual and narrow sense confined to unsworn statements used to prove the truth of facts declared, is by some judges and text writers applied in a wide sense to all statements by unexamined persons for whatever purpose tendered -i.e. as including the various declarations referred as original evidence."

Ancient Hindu Law on hearsay

The ancient lawgivers must have felt the necessity of admitting hearsay evidence under certain conditions, when direct evidence was not available.

Viṣṇu is the earliest lawgiver, who provides for conditional admission of hearsay evidence. He says -

"When an appointed witness is dead or has gone to another country, the evidence of a witness, who has heard him, may be admitted".⁴⁰

Here, the term 'appointed' needs explanation. An attesting witness to a document is an illustration of an 'appointed' witness. Even in other transaction, both parties to a transaction or contract, finding a certain reliable person present on the occasion request him to be a witness to the transaction or contract, with a view to calling him as a witness in the

³⁹ Taylor on Evince (1931 Edition), p.378

⁴⁰ उदिष्टसाक्षिणि मृते देशान्तरगते वा तदभिहितज्ञातारः प्रमाणम्॥ Viṣṇu VIII-12.

contingency of a future dispute or litigation such a witness may be called an appointed witness. If he has narrated the facts of the transaction to somebody (e.g. his own son), then a person's evidence after the death etc. of the appointed witness may be admitted and accepted in proof of the transaction or contract.

This proposition of Vishnu is rather too broad. What is the guarantee that the person, who is reported to have heard from the appointed witness, actually heard from the appointed witness or is giving a correct version of what he heard? Can such hearsay evidence be admitted in all types of cases?

Nārada on hearsay

Nārada classified hearsay witness into two broad categories viz. (a) Uttarasākṣin and (b) Mṛitāntara

Uttarasākṣin: An Uttarasākṣin is defined by Nārada in the same way as has been defined by Viṣṇu. If a witness dies, or goes abroad after having been appointed, those, who have heard him, may give evidence thereon indirect or secondary proof.⁴¹

Mṛitāntara: A Mṛitāntara witness can more appropriately be called a species of Uttarasākṣin witness. Mṛitāntara is defined as a witness, when the creditor or the claimant is no longer alive. Such a claim had to be transmitted to the witness. A Mṛitāntara witness, according to Nārada is not a competent witness. Nārada says "where can 'any person' bear testimony if the claimant is no longer alive? Such a person is not competent as a witness on account of intervening death."⁴²

Modern Indian law compared

To compare the above rule of Nārada with modern Indian law, section 32 of the Indian Evidence Act is quoted below – Section 32 statement by persons who cannot be called as witness.

"Statements, written or verbal, of relevant facts made by a person, who is dead, or who cannot be found, or who has become incapable of giving evidence, or whose evidence cannot be procured without an amount of delay or expense, which under the circumstances of the cases appears to the court to be unreasonable, are themselves relevant facts in the following cases –

1. When the statement is made by a person as to the cause of his death or as to any of the circumstances of the transaction, which resulted in his death, in cases in which the cause of that person's death becomes into question. Such statements are relevant, whether the person, who made them was, or was not, at the time, when

⁴¹ साक्ष्यदिष्टो यदि प्रयाद् गच्छेद् वाऽपि देशान्तरम्।

तच्छ्रोतारः प्रमाणं स्युः प्रमाणे ह्युत्तरा क्रिया॥ Nārada IV.167.

⁴² योऽर्थः श्रावयितव्यं स्यात्तस्मिन्मृतसति चार्थिनि।

क्व तद्वदतु साक्षित्वमित्वसाक्षी मृतान्तरम्॥ Nārada IV.162.

they were made, under expectation of death, and whatever may be the nature of the proceedings, in which the cause of death comes into question.

2. When the statement was made by such person in the ordinary course or business, and in particular, when it consists of any entry or memorandum made by him in books kept in the ordinary course of business, or in the discharge of professional duty; or of an acknowledgement written or signed by him of the receipt of money, goods, securities or properties of any kind; or of a document used in commerce written or signed by him; or of the date of a letter, or other document usually dated, written, or signed by him.
3. When the statement is against the pecuniary or proprietary interest of any person making it, or when, if true, it would expose him or would have exposed him to a criminal prosecution or to a suit for damages;
4. When the statement gives the opinion of any such person as to the existence of any public right or custom on matter of public or general interest, of the existence of which, if it existed, he would have been likely to be aware, and when such statement was made before any controversy as to such right, custom or matter arose.

Qualification of Witness

Modern law

Modern law does not provide for any special qualification of a good or proper witness. Section 118 of the Indian Evidence Act provides that ALL PERSONS shall be competent to testify unless the court considers that they are prevented from understanding the question put to them or from giving rational answers to those questions by tender years, extreme old age, disease, whether of body or mind or any other cause of the same kind.

The general rule is that the capacity of the person offered as a witness is presumed, i.e. to exclude a witness on the ground of mental or moral incapacity, the existence of the incapacity must be made to appear.

Ancient law

The ancient lawgivers lay down certain positive qualifications for witnesses with expectations for their credibility.

(a) Gautama on qualification

Gautama says – “Witnesses should be of unblemished character, not straying from the path of duty, those who can be relied on by the king, those who have no bias or prejudice either for or against either party to the litigation. The number of such witnesses must be more than two. He says persons of all castes are competent to testify.”⁴³

(b) Vasiṣṭha and Viṣṇu

Vasiṣṭha goes one step further by saying that witnesses should be Brāhmaṇas learned in the Vedas, should be beautiful and of good character, virtuous and truthful.⁴⁴ Vasiṣṭha,

⁴³ बहवः स्युरनिन्दितः, स्वकर्मसु प्रात्ययिका राङ्गाम्। निषप्रोत्यनमितापाश्रान्यतरस्मिन्। अपि क्षुदाः॥ Gautama XIII, 2.3.4.

⁴⁴ श्रोत्रियो रूपवान् शीलवान् गुणवान् सत्यवान् साक्षिणः। सर्वेषु सर्व एव वा। Vasiṣṭha quoted in Dharmakosha, p. 243.

here, is looking for the ideal witness in courts. Regarding caste qualifications, he says that in disputes between castes other than Brāhmaṇas, their own caste men are competent witnesses.

Viṣṇu similarly says that witnesses should be used to performing sacrifices and austerities, should have sons, should know dharma, should be studious, truthful and aged.⁴⁵

(c) **Manu and Yājñavalkya**

Manu lays down that witnesses should be householders and with sons, born in good families and know the matter in dispute, should be cited as witnesses, if they belong to the Kṣatriya, Vaiśya or Śūdra castes.⁴⁶

According to Yājñavalkya saintly and charitable persons, persons born in good families, truthful, religious minded, straightforward by nature are proper witnesses. They should be persons with sons and money.⁴⁷

Under Ancient Hindu Law Codes, the conditions required for the witness were strict and elaborate. We may conclude that the some ideas of the ancient principles or law codes as given by the ancient law compilers got reflected in the Modern Indian Law.

References :

1. Supakar, Shradhakar, *The Law of Evidence in Ancient India*, Punthi Pustak, Calcutta, 1990.
2. Banerjee, Santi, *Study in the Śatapatha Brāhmaṇa*, Sanskrit Pustak Bhandar, Kolkata, 1993.
3. Jolly, Julius, *Viṣṇu Smṛiti*, Chowkhamba Sanskrit series Office, Varanasi, 3rd Ed. 1962.
4. Nene, Gopal Shastri, *Manusmṛiti*, Chowkhamba Sanskrit series Office, Varanasi, 2nd Ed. 1970
5. Smṛititirtha, Narayan Chandra, *Nārada Smṛiti*, Sanskrit College, Calcutta, 1951
6. Taylor, A.P., *Treaties on the Law of Evidence as administered in England and Ireland* Sweet & Maxwell, 1993
7. Pandey, Umesh Chandra, *Gautama Dharmasūtrani*, Chowkhamba Sanskrit series Office, Varanasi, 1st Ed. 1966
8. Acharya, Narayan Ram, *Yājñavalkya Smṛiti with Mitākṣhara commentary*, 1949
9. Kane, Dr. P. V., *History of Dharmasastra*, Bhandarkar Oriental Research Institute Poona, Vol-III, 1946

⁵ कुलजातिवृत्तसंपन्ना यज्वानस्तपस्विनः पुत्रिणो धर्मशा अधीयानाः सत्यवन्तस्त्रैविद्यवृद्धाः ॥ Viṣṇu VIII.8

⁶ गृहिणः पुत्रिणो मौलाः क्षत्रवि शुद्रयोनयः।

अर्थज्ञाः साक्ष्यमद्वन्तिः न ये कैचिदनापदि ॥ Manu- VIII. 62.

⁷ तपस्विनो दानशीलाः कुलीनाः सत्यवादिनः।

धर्मप्रधानाः ऋजवः पुत्रवन्तो धनान्विताः ॥ yāj- II. 68